

LISTENING SKILLS. IMPROVING LISTENING PROFICIENCY

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Abstract: The article deals that the modern teaching with listening skills. Also, it is given the easy way improving languages listening skills below.

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INTRODUCTION

Among the other four skills, listening is the one that has been most forgotten and neglected in second language classrooms. So teachers don't pay much attention to this skill and teach it carelessly. In the field of language teaching and learning proficiency has tended to be viewed as the ability of speaking and writing in language in question. Listening and reading skills are in the second position. One reason for this situation might be the demanding characteristic of the listening skill. Listening has gained a new importance in language classrooms after spreading IT technology based information in society in Iran. Moreover it should be mentioned that most of the students' class time is devoted to the listening. Despite this, we often take importance of listening for granted, and it is the most overlooked skill among other skills. In natural order of learning any language, listening stands at first rank. Without any reception one can not produce anything. Though, if a teacher wants to have fluent and productive students, he/she should pay much and necessary attention to teaching listening skill.

Listening-Some of the teachers believe that speaking should be actively discouraged. One of the reasons of emphasizing listening and delaying speaking is

based on an opinion. Those who give importance to speaking view the language as a product and think that language is a behavior and speaking is the manifestation of this learning or happening. The modern effective methods of teaching listening skills to young learners include everything from interactive exercise to multimedia resources. Listening skills can best learn or improved through simple and engaging activities that focus more on the learning process instead of the final product. It doesn't matter you are working with small or large groups of students, you can use any of the following technique to develop your own methods for teaching students how to listen well.

Interpersonal activities

The non-threatening and effective way for students to develop stronger listening skills can be done by interpersonal activities such as mock interviews and storytelling.

Group activities

Large group activities also give the opportunity to the student to help through a helpful method for teaching listening skills to students. You can also begin with a simple group activity..

Audio segments

You can also teach listening skills to the students through audio segments such as radio programs, instructional lectures, online podcasts, and other audio messages.

Video segments

The other most helpful resource for teaching listening skills is video segments that include short sketches, documentary films, dramatic or comedic material, news programs, and interview segments.

Many students often encounter trouble in listening to foreign people even though they are doing well in the English classroom. Some students complain to teachers that, although they can understand what ALTs (Assistant Language Teachers)' are saying because they speak slowly and clearly, they cannot understand

what native English speakers are saying in real life. Why does this problem happen? What is wrong with the teaching of listening in Japanese schools? The first and probably the biggest problem is that, although the importance of listening skills is widely acknowledged in Japan, the adequate teaching and materials to develop them have not been provided. In a typical listening lesson, students either listen just to the taped script of a reading textbook or, after listening to some materials, they answer multiple choice questions based on the content of listening materials. In this kind of lesson, -correct answers are emphasized, but the listening process necessary to decode the information is ignored, and the kinds of skills and strategies for effective listening are not practiced. That is, students are just tested on their own ability to answer correctly and are not taught how to listen to English. Second, the amount of time for listening lessons is limited in English I and II, compared with reading, writing, and speaking. For example, it is estimated that the average time devoted to listening activities in every class is 5 minutes per day. Students are not sufficiently exposed to a variety of authentic materials, either. In short, although they are accustomed to English spoken clearly and slowly in classroom materials and can understand it, they get embarrassed and frustrated when they encounter real English which is spoken at a normal speed. Third, they are not used to the difference between spoken English and written English. Spoken English has different features such as ungrammatical utterances, false starts, hesitation, assimilation, and redundancy. If they aren't familiar with those phenomena, they may not be able to listen to English and understand it.

Lastly, in listening lessons, teachers don't have the specific notion that listening should be integrated with other skills, i.e., speaking, reading, and writing. When real world communication is examined, we never finish verbal communication appropriately without doing something after listening. For example, when we have a conversation with someone, we have to respond to him or her. It is never just oneway communication. In a situation like a lecture in which students are listening to the instructor, they usually take notes. We can think of many other

situations in which listening is integrated with the other three skills. In real world communication, that is, listening, speaking, reading, and writing are interrelated and interdependent.

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